

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN WITH SOFT TISSUE INJURIES OF THE ORAL CAVITY

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Relevance: The result of the research was a generalization and analysis of the indicators of local immunity of the oral cavity observed in children of primary school age with damage to the soft tissues of the oral cavity, and the results of identifying representatives of the normative microflora of a given biotope.

The studied baby fluid was taken using traditional methods, determining the relative parameters of its cellular composition (lymphocytes, monocytes, band and segmented neutrophils), as well as the concentrations of IgA and lactoferrin from this biological substance. As a result of bacteriological studies, representatives of normal and transient microflora of the oral cavity were collected in genera and species manifestations.

Key words: children of primary school age, lymphocytes, monocytes, rod and segmental purulent neutrophils, IgA and lactoferrin, pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms

Purpose of the study: Development of diagnostic and prognostic criteria based on clinical and immunological characteristics in children of primary school age with lesions of the soft tissues of the oral cavity.

Research materials:

During the research, 184 patients aged 6 to 11 years were studied, who were divided into the following groups:

The first group consisted of 52 patients aged 6-11 years with damage to the soft tissues of the oral cavity caused by chemical exposure in an acute condition;

The second group consisted of 77 patients aged 6-12 years with damage to the soft tissues of the oral cavity caused by mechanical impact during chronic;

Third group – (control) - 55 patients 6-12 years old without change

Research methods: When performing the work, clinical, microbiological, immunological, and statistical studies were used.

Result of the study: The effect of damage to the soft tissues of the oral cavity by mechanical and chemical effects on the local immunity of the oral cavity, including the cellular composition of oral resistance factors and humoral factors,

was studied. Along with this, it is important to study the state of the oral microflora, which is inextricably linked with quantitative indicators of the cellular composition and humoral factors of the oral cavity, with the duration of the disease and complications of this pathology. We should not forget that the normative microflora of this biotope has a positive effect on the local immune status, which is also essential for its regulation.

Conclusion.

1. In sick children, lesions of the soft tissues of the oral cavity with gram-negative cocci (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*) and gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter* spp, *Proteus* spp, *Klebsiella* spp) are observed; its levels were determined at 1.20 - 5.29 times higher than in healthy children.
2. Pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms were detected in healthy children in a small percentage ($6.67 \pm 13.33\%$), pathogenic cocci were distinguished by high quantitative identification (73.33%), which indicated differences in the intensity of occurrence of constant amounts of transient microflora.
3. Increased rates of detection of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms when identifying lesions of the soft tissues of the oral cavity indicate that an inflammatory process has developed in the oral cavity; local immune factors are not able to provide adequate protection.
4. An increased percentage of detection of gram-negative pathogenic cocci (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram-negative pathogenic bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) is recommended as a microbiological diagnostic criterion for the likelihood of formation and risk of developing purulent-inflammatory diseases in the oral cavity.

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